

Hospital Discharge Decisions and the Implications on Patient Outcomes in Italy

Authors: *Yuxi Wang, Luigi Siciliani, Aleksandra Torbica, and Simone Ghislandi*

ABSTRACT

Objective: Italy is characterised by a highly decentralised and heterogeneous health care provision landscape. This disparity may result in systematically different hospital discharge behaviours that encroach the horizontal equity of the health care system. The objectives of this paper are three-fold. First, we want to identify whether the risk-adjusted hospitalisation length-of-stay (LOS) has a causal impact on the probability of unplanned patient readmission. Second, we want to observe the heterogeneous effects across hospital types, the timing of the year and across regions. Finally, we want to understand how financial incentives affect the discharge decision by identifying the cost-related trade-offs.

Methods: We use hospital discharge data from 2010 to 2015 on all elderly patients admitted for Acute Myocardial Infarction in Italy with some exclusion criteria. We first analyse the causal impact of LOS on patient outcomes using a two-stage-least-square model with a constructed instrumental variable that proxies capacity constraint. We then include indicators for hospital ownership, months of the year and regions in our baseline models for patient outcomes. Based on a theoretical cost-minimisation model, we further employ a two-part empirical model to investigate the differences in the cost and quality trade-off across hospitals with a prospective payment system, with and without penalty for readmission, and a global budgeting system.

Results: Preliminary findings show that risk-adjusted LOS effectively reduces the probability of readmission and the effects are stronger for hospital trust and teaching hospitals than local health authority-managed hospital units. There is substantial regional heterogeneity, with regions under stricter budget constraints exhibiting less significant effects of the protective role of longer LOS. We expect the effect to be the strongest towards the end of the budgetary year, reflecting that potential changes of discharge behaviour in response to the financial incentives can have implications on patient outcomes. For the analysis of cost and quality trade-offs, we find that on average, the marginal cost of one more hospitalisation stay is larger than the expected cost from future readmission, indicating that overall, increasing LOS, although reduces the probability of readmission, does not reduce the overall episode cost. We further expect that hospitals under a prospective-payment system coupled with early readmission penalties to be the most cost-efficient in preventing readmission.

Discussion: The results shed light not only on the mechanism behind the disparity in healthcare provision but also provide insights on the optimal design of the payment system in aligning the providers' behaviour to improve quality of care.